

Title: Ethnography among young Ukrainian nationals in Warsaw: Interviews and participant observations

• **Description:** Interviews with Ukrainian nationals who were predominantly students or student workers in Warsaw ($N = 30$, 20–26 years old). The data includes interviews with the young people who moved from Ukraine to Warsaw both before and after Russia's full-scale invasion. The data also includes a field diary with the notes from participant observations in the bus and railway stations, and humanitarian spaces.

Date of data collection or date of publication: The data was collected between 2020 and 2023.

- **Keywords:** Ukraine, labour migration, forced displacement, refugees
- **At least one Author** Daria Krivonos, University of Helsinki
- **At least one Publication**

Krivonos, D. (2022). Carrying Europe's 'White Burden', Sustaining Racial Capitalism: Young Post-Soviet Migrant Workers in Helsinki and Warsaw. *Sociology*, 57(4), 865-881. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00380385221122413> (Original work published 2023)

- **Description of where the data is or will be stored**

The data is stored in the university OneDrive folder protected by a password.